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A novel analogue of Asinger reaction for the synthesis of thiazinoquinoline derivatives

Zeinab Faghihi¹, Hossein Abdi Oskooie¹, Majid M. Heravi¹, Mahmoud Tajbakhsh², [Morteza Shiri](#)¹

1 Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran 1993893973, Iran.

2 Department of Chemistry, University of Mazandaran, Babolsar, Iran.

Abstract

The unexpected synthesis of 2H-[1,3]thiazino[6,5-b]quinoline derivatives from domino cyclic condensation of 2-mercaptoquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and ammonium acetate at ambient temperature in EtOH was described.

Graphical abstract

Keywords: Cyclization, Condensation, 2-Mercaptoquinoline-3-carbaldehydes, Thiazinoquinoline, Catalyst-free, Asinger reaction.